
INSTITUTIONAL REPOSITORIES IN ACADEMIC LIBRARIES

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Abstract:

The purpose of this paper is to information of Institutional Repositories about concept of Institutional Repositories, elements of Institutional Repositories, Content of Institutional Repositories, free and open source repositories software, Advantages of Developing Institutional Repository, Problems Associated with Institutional Repositories, Measures for Successful Institutional Repositories and role of Libraries in Institutional Repositories in academic libraries.

Keywords: *Institutional Repository, Scholarly Content, Free and Open Source Repository Software, IPR.*

Introduction:

Today we are living in the age of information Revolution. There have been a lot of changes in library and information activities in the world. The changes in the late 90s and thereafter have been very fast. Old technologies of information exchange are being replaced by new technologies and methods. Basically two fundamental changes have been observed by the library; (i) The abundance of the digital resources and (ii) Development of ICTs. The demands of information users and researchers are increasing day-by-day. The old information delivery and seeking methods are being replaced by applying new modified technology-based methods. In this age, internet become an essential medium for information exchange and with its help anyone can communicate his/her information with another at anywhere in the world to maintain scholarly communication. The

tremendous growth of Internet and www, high resolution capture devices, highly capacity digital storage media, multifaceted search engine, fast and increased bandwidth network have forced librarians and information professionals to integrate them and develop new methods, like open access, digital publishing and self-archiving and academic digital repositories. Institutional Repositories are an emerging trend among institutions of higher education as a tool to make knowledge bank of an institutions intellectual output to the global community via the internet. An institutional Repository (IR) is a digital collection of a university's scholarly and creative output. IR is a part of larger global information system of repositories providing the foundation for a new model of scholarly publishing.

Objective of the Study:

1. To study about the Institutional Repository (IR).
2. To study about the elements of Institutional Repository.
3. To find out the content of Institutional Repository.
4. To know about the free and open Repository software
5. To study about the Advantages of Developing Institutional Repository.
6. To find out the Problems Associated with Institutional Repositories.
7. To study about the Measures for Successful Institutional Repositories.
8. To know about the role of Libraries in Institutional Repositories.

Institutional Repository (IR):

Repository means formally organized and managed collection of digital content generated by faculty, staff and students of an institution. The main purpose of institutional repositories is to bring together and preserve the intellectual output of the academic community. IR is a set of services than institute offers to the members of its community for the management and dissemination of digital materials created by the institution and its community. IR may contain the intellectual works of faculty and students-both research and teaching materials and also documentation of the activities of the institution itself in the form of records of events and performance and of the ongoing intellectual life of the institution.

According to the SPAR, an IR is a digital archive of the research output of faculty, researchers and students of an institution and usually accessible freely to

end users both within and outside of the institution.

Some of the main objectives for having an institutional repository are to provide [open access](#) to institutional research output by [self-archiving](#) in an [open access repository](#), to create global visibility for an institution's scholarly research, and to store and preserve other institutional digital assets, including unpublished or otherwise easily lost literature such as theses, working papers or technical reports.

Elements of Institutional Repository (IR):

A digital institutional repository could be any collection of digital material hosted, owned or controlled or disseminated by an institute. So, the content of an institutional repository is:

Institutionally defined: IR represent an historical and tangible embodiment of the intellectual life and output of an institution.

Scholarly Content: This may include pre-prints and other works in progress, peer reviewed articles, monographs, conference papers, theses and dissertations etc.

Comulative and perpetual: IR aims to preserve and make accessible digital content on a long term basis.

Open and interoperable: IR system must be able to support interoperability in order to provide access via multiple search engines and other discovery tools.

Content of an Institutional Repository:

- Pre-prints of articles or research reports submitted for publication.
- The text of articles accepted for publication in journals.

- Revised of published work with comments for academic readers.
- Conference papers.
- Teaching materials.
- Student project.
- Doctoral thesis and dissertations.
- Database resulting for research projects.
- Committee papers.
- Works of Art.
- Photographs and video recordings.

Free and Open Source Repository Software:

- **Archimedes-** Laval University Library
- **Artudis-** Erasmus University, Rotterdam
- **Diatss-** Cornell Digital Library Research Group
- **DSpace-** Dspace foundation
- **EPrints-** Free Software
- **ETD-db-** Virginia Tech University Libraries
- **Fedora-** Fedora commons
- **Greenstone-** New Zealand Digital Library Project, University of Wankato
- **IRPlus-** University of Rochester
- **SWORD-**

Advantages of Developing Institutional Repository:

The main advantages of Institutional Repositories are:

For Users

- Expansion of the range of shared knowledge.
- Opportunities to simplify and extend dissemination.

For Contributor

- Greater citation, digital platform to publish publications, preservation

of the publications in digital form, to easy reuse.

For institution

- Enabling of IPR to be exploited more effectively at Institutional level.
- Flexible ways to develop exiting scholarly communications.
- Opportunities for new forms of scholarly communications.
- Flexible ways to develop existing scholarly communications.

For Researcher Community

- The research community will be able to access the worlds research available in different Institutional Repositories.
- IR helps for faster communication and reduces the unwanted duplication.

Problems Associated with Institutional Repositories

- **Lack of proper policy-** A crucial part is deciding what to collect, what to store, what to preserve and what to discard is to be addressed.
- Insufficient funds for required IT Infrastructure for refreshing and migration and trained manpower.
- Protocols for interoperability and software are delicate.
- As the IR is bookshelves of digital content none of the storage media can be guaranteed to last long.
- Time consuming and lengthy deposition procedure for its management leads to the authors and publishers annoyed.
- Sustainability is the major issue.
- Lack of awareness and copyright infringement is also an issue to overcome.

Measures for Successful Institutional Repositories:

Following measures are necessary in building successful Institutional Repositories viz., eight “C” words:

1. **Comprehension:** Workforce must share and understand the scope and purpose of the repository.
2. **Collaboration:** Collaboration involves thinking and working together to contribute scholarly communication and to solve the common problems.
3. **Context:** Each employee has a unique mind set and education, work culture and experience helps them to integrate for contribution.
4. **Change:** Mould employee to feel as an institutional asset for intellectual capital deposition.
5. **Caring:** Motivate them to share their contribution for dissemination and growth.
6. **Commitment:** For continuous growth and funding in time without end.
7. **Creativity:** Constellation of an imaginary object and to visualize them.
8. **Competence:** Know-how of IR elements and its functions.

Role of Libraries:

The library plays a crucial role in an information society connecting, integrating and managing informational resources. The value of the library for the academic community is not less than in pre-Internet days, but far greater in the present era. Librarians have always been engaged in managing and developing their collection. LIS professionals are always in front of new technology and they accept it

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and trying to develop their library services. Librarians have long experience for collection building and maintain the information. Institutional Repository and open access will be the next challenges for library and LIS professionals. As a result libraries have to play vital role in building institutional repositories. Libraries are able to provide direct access to scholarly publication via IR rather than any other. The Institutional Repositories are successful because of its new information and current information. Its related with producer of creating the associated metadata and the libraries the lead role in development of the institutional repositories and their normalization with collection management. Institutional Repositories needs satisfactory and trained staffing support having knowledge of Institutional repository and to overcome this problem library would have to train their staff member or would have to require librarians who have good knowledge about IR and who can handle well digital collection management.

Conclusion:

Institutional repositories are one of the most promising developments that utilize new web technologies to offer a viable and sustainable alternative to the current model of scholarly publishing. The repositories also serve as a comprehensive publication database of the parent's organization. The aim of Institutional Repositories is to aid the management and

dissemination of the scholarly electronic resources produced by academics. Institutional Repository is an electronic archive of the scientific and scholarly outputs of an institution. Development of IR has emerged as new strategy in universities and research organizations and its growth is fast. Academic Institutes are managing to compile the intellectual output of the institute published in different forms like articles in journals, technical reports, processing, historical record, manuscripts, rare collection, theses and dissertations, teaching material, research notes/data/information. Since software like Dspace are available free it is easy to create a repository.

Institutional Repositories has brought an illustrative changes and wider opening in the field of scholarly publication. Development of IR has received a little leverage from the workforce and publishers for change and commitment. The IR acts as seamless tool to capture, store, preserve and to access intellectual capital of scholars. Further, it simplifies the process of global access to local information. There is no doubt that the open access features of IR could contribute significantly to economic growth by broadening the area of market for scholarly publications.

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